

1 **Risk Analysis for Alien Taxa framework for the South African NEM:BA A&IS**
2 **Regulations (v2.0)**

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95 **General guidance**

96

97 The questions for completing the risk analysis are described here in detail. For each
98 question, the corresponding section in the Reporting template (Supplementary
99 Material, Appendix S5) needs to be filled in, generally consisting of Response,
100 Confidence, Comments/Rationale, and References. Unless otherwise stated, all
101 these sections need to be filled in.

102 Each statement needs to be justified, either with references from the literature or
103 personal communication (e.g., information provided by experts). Specifically, justify
104 the responses given with available evidence. Primary references should be used
105 throughout to justify answers, if available. If secondary references are used, this
106 needs to be noted and justified (for example if primary reference is not accessible).
107 Do not cite sources which you have not read or understood. Use direct quotations
108 sparingly and appropriately, and put them in quotation marks. Do not paste
109 quotations from papers unless they contribute directly or are necessary to
110 understand the Response provided. A glossary of terms used in the framework is
111 provided in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S1.

112

113 **Formatting**

114

115 All text in the risk analysis should be written in South African English. Arial font size
116 10 should be used throughout. Numbers less or equal to ten should be written in
117 words. Check spelling and grammar.

118 All pictures, maps, figures and data used need to be appropriately referenced. Maps
119 drawn using GBIF should include a DOI of the download
120 (<https://www.gbif.org/citation/guidelines>), not just a web-link to the *Taxon*.

121 All references cited in the text need to be provided in the references section of the
122 respective question. References should be listed in alphabetical order, and they
123 need to be formatted according to ABC Bothalia style (=Harvard), including the DOI.
124 To find a DOI, use the following link: <https://doi.crossref.org/simpleTextQuery>.

125 Personal communications should not be listed in the reference list but provided in the
126 Rationale.

127 The *Taxon* name should be used consistently throughout the document, and either
128 the scientific (latin) name or common name should be used. If scientific name is
129 used, the genus name should be abbreviated after first use, except at the start of a
130 sentence. Latin species and genus names need to be italicised throughout.

131 In the Response sections, capitalise your response and provide it in full including the
132 probability or abbreviation respectively, e.g., “Fairly probable (p=0.5)” for LIK1-6, and
133 “Moderate (MO)” for CON1-3.

134

135

136 **Summary page**

137

138 The summary page is filled in last, after all other sections are compiled. It needs to
139 be maximum one page long and highlights the key factors that lead to the overall
140 recommendation (rather than summarising all the information provided in the risk
141 analysis). It is divided into three main sections: 1) Risk assessment summary; 2)
142 Risk management; and 3) Recommendations. The following paragraphs outline
143 which information each of these sections needs to contain.

144

145 *Risk assessment summary*

146 A summary of the LIK and CON questions are needed, and the outcome of Table 2
147 is provided. Essentially, the following questions needs to be answered: Is the *Taxon*
148 in the *Area*? How widespread is the *Taxon*? How was it introduced into the *Area*?
149 How could it be introduced in future? What are the recorded and potential
150 environmental and socio-economic impacts of the *Taxon* in the *Area* and elsewhere?

151

152 *Risk management summary*

153 Report on the main findings from the MAN sections which includes benefits,
154 stakeholders involved, and whether the risk can be reduced under specific
155 conditions. Mention if conflicts between stakeholders are expected. Also refer to the
156 questions on eradication feasibility as appropriate. Note if risk can be reduced by
157 permitting, or if exemptions and prohibitions are in order.

158

159 *Recommendations*

160 Outline the recommendations and the reasons for arriving at them. Follow and refer
161 to the decision tree in Figure 3 when appropriate, and the explanations in REC1.
162 Also note here if stakeholder engagement is likely needed (based on MAN2). If there
163 is substantial uncertainty about the recommendation it is important to specify what
164 should be done to resolve the uncertainty, and specifically if the recommendation is
165 for the *Taxon* to be re-evaluated within a certain timeframe be clear about what is
166 needed to resolve current uncertainties. The recommendation section provides the
167 arguments, the sections under this provide the specifics: the recommended
168 category, whether a change to the nomenclature is required (this can include
169 changes to the common name), and whether the recommendation should be
170 revisited in 5 years.

171

172

173

174 **1. Background**

175

176 The background gives important information on the assessor(s) and expert(s)
177 consulted, which ensures the review conducted after submission of the analysis is
178 transparent, independent and communication for revisions of the analysis is
179 straightforward. Note that information on the assessor(s) and experts is redacted
180 upon submission of the risk analysis to the Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the
181 Environment for their consideration, and the authorship of the document is changes
182 to be SANBI. Furthermore, it describes the *Area* for which the risk analysis is
183 conducted, and the *Taxon*, including where it is present (native and alien range), and
184 how it is moved around (pathways).

185 The region for which the risk analysis is performed is referred to as the *Area*. In most
186 cases, analyses will be undertaken at a national level (e.g., South Africa), but the
187 structure of the framework allows the analyses to be undertaken for different spatial
188 units (e.g. for a national park or for the southern African region). The *Area* must be
189 clearly specified and all questions referring to the *Area* specifically consider
190 information with respect to the region chosen.

191 The taxon under assessment is referred to as the *Taxon*. The *Taxon* can be a
192 species, sub-species, infra-specific entity, genus or any other taxonomic level. Risk
193 analyses are mostly carried out on individual species as a standard taxonomic entity
194 as, mostly, this is the level at which information is available, but this is not always
195 appropriate, feasible or desirable. For example, different taxonomic levels are
196 preferable: if the taxonomy of a group is not well resolved; if species are difficult to
197 distinguish but the whole group (i.e. genus or family) poses a significant threat (e.g.
198 certain taxa of mites or plant pathogenic rust fungi); and if there are important
199 differences between sub-species or infra-specific entities. Ideally the analysis should
200 consider whatever taxonomic grouping for which the risk is the same, though in
201 practice, this is very hard to achieve and species level assessments are therefore
202 most common.

203

204

205 ***BAC1 Name of assessor(s)***

206 Give the full name and surname of the lead assessor and any additional assessors. Note which of the
207 assessors is the corresponding assessor, i.e., who should be contacted during the review process
208 and if questions are raised in future [note: generally the lead assessor is the assessor for
209 correspondence]. Add more lines if more assessors were involved.

210

211

212 ***BAC2 Contact details of assessor(s)***

213 Provide the contact details of the assessors listed. Add more lines if more assessors were involved.

214

215

216 ***BAC3 Name(s) and contact details of expert(s) consulted***

217 The NEM:BA A&IS Regulations require the input of at least one expert into a risk analysis report.
218 Therefore, it is mandatory for experts to be consulted during the risk analysis process. Add details of
219 the experts consulted for the risk analysis. This can include internal (within same organisation or
220 group of assessors) or external (including international) people who influenced, commented or
221 amended the document before submission. Note that the experts listed must have agreed to be listed
222 here and provided substantial input into the document. The risk analysis report should not list experts
223 that were not contacted or who made only a minor contribution (e.g., verification of a museum
224 specimen, or confirmation of a minor detail in the risk analysis report). In the comments, outline the
225 kind of contribution these experts made. These can be contributions to the whole assessment or only

226 specific sections or questions. Furthermore, clarify why the listed people are considered experts, i.e.
227 what expertise they bring to the table. Add additional lines if several experts were consulted.

228
229

230 ***BAC4 Scientific name of Taxon under assessment***

231 Note the biological entity under consideration. The full scientific (Latin binomial) name as well as
232 taxonomic authority of the accepted name is required. For all subspecific entities please include
233 "subsp." between the genus and species names, this is often not included for animal names (it is
234 implied), but for consistency across taxa and to ensure compatibility with GBIF the full version of the
235 name is preferred here. In cases of subspecific entities, create additional rows and have 'Authority
236 (species):' on one row and 'Authority (subspecies):' on the next row.

237 Note in the Comments if the scientific name in the current NEM:BA A&IS Regulations differs from the
238 accepted name, and cross-reference to BAC15. As a default for plants check the Botanical Database
239 of Southern Africa (BODATSA) (<http://posa.sanbi.org/>) and Plants of the World Online
240 (<https://powo.science.kew.org/>); for all other taxa follow the taxonomy in GBIF (<https://www.gbif.org/>)
241 unless there is an argued reason to use a different taxonomy. Check against the current lists
242 developed as part of the national status report on biological invasions and their management in South
243 Africa (<https://zenodo.org/record/7638966>).

244 In most cases, the *Taxon* under assessment is a species, but it could be another taxonomic level
245 (e.g., genus or sub-species). Mention the taxonomic level under comments. The organism under
246 assessment will be called the "*Taxon*" in the rest of the document. It is important to note in the
247 references which database was used for the species identification/name.

248
249

250 ***BAC5 Synonym(s) considered***

251 List synonyms of the scientific (Latin) name of the *Taxon* which were considered for this assessment.
252 Make sure to include the name as used in the current and previous NEM:BA A&IS Regulations,
253 especially if different to the accepted name (cross-check with BAC15). Only list names included in the
254 literature search, not synonyms which were not considered in this risk analysis document. Check for
255 synonyms in ITIS (<http://www.itis.gov/>) or a taxon specific taxonomic database. Indicate in the
256 comments why the synonyms listed were included. Note in the references which database was
257 considered.

258
259

260 ***BAC6 Common name(s) considered***

261 List common names of the *Taxon* which were considered for this assessment. Only list names
262 included in the literature search, not all recorded common names. In the comments, indicate where
263 the common names are used, and which languages were considered.

264
265

266 ***BAC7 What is the native range of the Taxon?***

267 Describe the *Taxon's* native range. If it is found in many countries, provide native regions or
268 continents in the Response, and list each country in the Comments. If the *Taxon's* native range
269 includes the *Area* or part of the *Area*, see BAC9. The *Taxon's* biogeographic distribution provides
270 useful context for understanding the actual and potential range of the *Taxon*. Provide a confidence
271 level for the response based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material (Appendix S2)
272 and justify the level given in the Comments.

273 A map of the native range should be provided. If the map is available in a file, please insert a low
274 resolution copy (<1MB) as an appendix to the Reporting template and provide the file name and (if
275 possible) a link to a higher resolution copy. Provide a clear legend with the map and describe where
276 the data came from, including a reference if applicable, and note if there are any inconsistencies
277 between data sources. Please check that there are no discrepancies between the maps and the text,
278 and explain any differences.

279
280

281 ***BAC8 What is the global alien range of the Taxon?***

282 Describe the *Taxon's* global alien range. If it is found in many countries, provide regions or continents
283 in the Response, and list each country in the Comments. This includes the *Taxon's* global alien range,

284 including the range within the *Area*. The distribution of the *Taxon*'s alien range provides useful context
285 for understanding the actual and potential range of the *Taxon* and provides guidance for the literature
286 search. Provide a confidence level for the response given based on the guidelines provided in the
287 Supplementary Material, Appendix S2 and justify the level given in the Comments.
288 A map of the alien range should be provided in an Appendix. If the map is available in a file, please
289 insert a low resolution copy (<1MB) as an appendix to the Reporting template and provide the file
290 name and (if possible) a link to a higher resolution copy. Provide a clear legend with the map and
291 describe where the data came from, including reference if applicable, and note if there are any
292 inconsistencies between data sources. In particular, the *Taxon* might not be recorded in the *Area* in
293 the database(s) on which the map is based, but the *Taxon*'s presence is confirmed in other sources.
294 This needs to be clearly stated in the legend to avoid confusion. Check for discrepancies between the
295 maps and the text and explain any discrepancies in the figure legend.

296
297

298 ***BAC9 Geographic scope = the Area under consideration***

299 Specify the geographic entity under consideration, i.e. the geographic scope of the assessment. In
300 most cases this will be the whole of South Africa, but it can also be only a part of the country, for
301 example a single province, a national park or a river catchment. The region under assessment will
302 hereafter be referred to as the "*Area*". The *Taxon* should generally only be assessed in its alien range
303 for the purpose of this risk analysis. If the *Taxon*'s native range includes parts of the country, clarify
304 here that only alien ranges are considered for this assessment (i.e. set the *Area* to include only the
305 part of the country where the *Taxon* is alien).

306
307

308 ***BAC10 Is the Taxon present in the Area?***

309 Note if the *Taxon* is present anywhere in the *Area*. If the *Taxon* is currently listed as Category 2 and
310 any permits have been issued to keep, trade, etc. the *Taxon* is assumed to be present in the *Area*. In
311 such cases provide a cross-reference to MAN2 where the details are to be provided. In the case
312 where the presence of the *Taxon* is not confirmed by any source, note in the Comments all the
313 sources that were consulted. Provide a confidence level for the Response based on the guidelines
314 given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2 and justify the level given in the Comments. It is
315 important to link the text in BAC10 to the evidence laid out in BAC1.

316 A map of the *Taxon*'s alien range in the *Area* should be provided in an Appendix. If the map is
317 available in a file, please insert a low resolution copy (<1MB) as an appendix to the Reporting
318 template and provide the file name and (if possible) a link to a higher resolution copy. Provide a clear
319 legend with the map and describe where the data came from, including reference if applicable, and
320 note if there are any inconsistencies between data sources. Also indicate, if the data are available,
321 where the *Taxon* is present in captivity or cultivation, and where it is outside of captivity/cultivation.
322 Check for discrepancies between the maps and the text, highlight and discuss any discrepancies in
323 the figure legend (cf. BAC8).

324
325

325 ***Response options:***

326 Yes: There is evidence that the *Taxon* is present in the *Area*.
327 No: There is no evidence that the *Taxon* is present in the *Area*.

328
329

330 ***BAC11 Evidence of presence***

331 This provides the details used to score BAC10. This should include notes on whether there is a
332 physical specimen available, molecular confirmation that the specimen is the *Taxon*, whether there is
333 a literature record of presence of the specimen. Provide source, and whether there has been recent
334 field confirmation, and specify which sources were searched even if there is no physical specimen
335 available from the *Area*.

336 Under Source, in each case provide details of where the data are from. For example in the case of
337 physical specimens list the relevant collection and accession numbers (Herbarium – XXXXXX;
338 Accession – XXXXXX) and also include the person at the herbarium/museum who identified the
339 sample and date. Museums can assist with museum records of animal species. Note that this can
340 also include live specimens in zoological and botanical gardens.

341
342

342 ***Response options:***

343 Yes: such a record exists (e.g., a physical specimen of the *Taxon* is available which was collected in
344 the *Area*)
345 No: there is no such record (e.g., no physical specimen of the *Taxon* is available that was collected in
346 the *Area*).
347 Unclear: there are some data, but the results are not clear (e.g., molecular results might indicate
348 several potential taxa or a field observation might only be to a genus level).
349 NE: Not evaluated, there has been no attempt to look to see if such data have been collected or not
350

351 ***BAC12 Is the Taxon native to the Area or part of the Area?***

352 Indicate whether the *Taxon* is native to at least part of the *Area* and select one of the Response
353 options below for each (yes, no, or don't know). If "don't know" is the response, no confidence is
354 provided. Else, provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary
355 Material, Appendix S2 and justify the level given in the Comments.

356 If the *Taxon* is native to any part of the *Area*, it should not be considered for listing under the NEM:BA
357 A&IS Regulations in the *Area*, rather the assessment area should be changed to only include the
358 alien range of the *Taxon*. For example, if the *Taxon* is native to the mainland but alien to off-shore
359 islands (e.g., the Prince Edward Islands), listing should only be considered for those islands, i.e. the
360 *Area* (as specified under BAC7) should be the islands. Similarly, if the *Taxon* is native to some
361 provinces, but alien in others, the assessment should only include the alien provinces as the *Area*,
362 and the *Taxon* should be regulated at a provincial rather than a national level.

363 ***Response options:***

364 Yes: The *Taxon* is native to (part of) the *Area*.
365 No: The *Taxon* is not native to (part of) the *Area*.
366 Don't know: The native/alien status of the *Taxon* in the *Area* is unknown.
367
368
369

370 ***BAC13 What is the Taxon's introduction status in the Area?***

371 To what degree is the *Taxon*, surviving, reproducing, and has expanded its range in its alien range in
372 the *Area*? This is based on the framework of Blackburn et al. (2011).

- 373 - captive or cultivated: individuals transported beyond the limits of its native range and in captivity,
374 quarantine, or cultivation, i.e., individuals provided with conditions suitable for them, but explicit
375 measures of containment or explicit measures to prevent spread are in place. This includes pests
376 present on captive organisms.
- 377 - released or escaped (i.e., present outside of captivity or cultivation): individuals transported beyond
378 the limits of native range and directly released into the new environment, or individuals escaped
379 from cultivation/captivity
- 380 - established: individuals surviving outside of cultivation/captivity in locations where introduced,
381 reproduction occurring, and population self-sustaining
- 382 - invasive: self-sustaining populations outside of cultivation/captivity with individuals surviving and
383 reproducing a significant distance from the original point of introduction, i.e., dispersal happening.

384 Give information on each step in the invasion continuum and select one of the Responses outlines
385 below for each (yes, no, don't know). If "don't know" is the response, no confidence is provided. Else,
386 provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2
387 and justify the level given in the Comments.
388

389 ***Response options:***

390 Yes: The *Taxon* has reached (at least) that stage in the invasion continuum in the *Area*.
391 No: The *Taxon* has not reached that stage in the invasion continuum in the *Area*, or it was never or is
392 no longer in that stage, (e.g. captivity or cultivation).
393 Don't know: It is unknown whether the *Taxon* has reached this stage in the invasion continuum in the
394 *Area*.
395
396

397 ***BAC14 How did (or does) the Taxon arrive in the Area?***

398 List historical and current pathways along which the *Taxon* was or is introduced to the *Area*. The
399 pathway classification is based on the one by Harrower et al. (2017) with the terms adopted by the
400 CBD (see Supplementary Material, Appendix S3). Harrower et al. (2017) provided detailed guidance
401 for the situations under which each pathway category applies and the document should be consulted

402 when scoring this section. List all pathway sub-categories within each broad category as laid out in
403 Supplementary Material, Appendix S3. Provide evidence for each pathway listed. Add additional rows
404 to the reporting template if more sub-categories apply.
405 Provide a confidence level for each sub-category applicable based on the guidelines given in the
406 Supplementary Material, Appendix S2 and justify the level given in the Comments.

407

408 **Response options:**

409 Select the relevant pathways from Supplementary Material Appendix S3, with one row per pathway.
410 If the *Taxon* is not present and has never been present in the *Area*, the pathway should be scored as
411 “NA”; if there are no known pathways, it should be scored as “Don’t know”

412

413

414 ***BAC15 Is the Taxon regulated in the Area?***

415 Is the *Taxon* regulated in the *Area*, or was it regulated in the past? If yes, provide details. The
416 regulatory name should be taken verbatim and a note made if it differs from the nomenclature used in
417 BAC4. It is important to look for synonyms used in the past or names misapplied as these might need
418 to be used in searches for material. For the other sections, also take the wording verbatim directly
419 from the relevant regulatory lists (e.g., <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8160209>; or Wilson (2023)
420 for NEM:BA A&IS Lists, navigating to the most recent version as appropriate).

421

422 **Response options:**

423 Yes: The *Taxon* is currently regulated in the *Area*, or was regulated in the past.

424 No: The *Taxon* was never regulated in the *Area*.

425

426 **2. Likelihood**

427

428 This section deals with the likelihood of the *Taxon* to enter (LIK1 & LIK2), establish
 429 (LIK3 & LIK4) and spread (LIK5 & LIK6) in the *Area*, which is representing the steps
 430 alien taxa need to take in order to become invasive. This section therefore assesses
 431 the likelihood of the *Taxon* to become invasive. The timeframe to be considered for
 432 these questions is 10 years. In other words, we are assessing the likelihood of these
 433 events to occur within the next 10 years.

434 All the answers are described in scenarios for each level separately, with each level
 435 being an order of magnitude more likely than the next lower level. If the answer is
 436 unknown, it is set as $p = 1$, applying the precautionary principle (i.e., a high likelihood
 437 is set if evidence is lacking to answer the question).

438 Generally, all the answers in this section are structured in the same way, and they
 439 follow the logic described here:

440

- 441 • Extremely unlikely ($p = 0.000001$): as likely as winning the lottery if you play it
 442 once
- 443 • Very unlikely ($p = 0.0027$): as likely as a new person you meet having their
 444 birthday on the same day as yours
- 445 • Unlikely ($p = 0.027$): as likely as rolling two sixes when playing dice
- 446 • Fairly probable ($p = 0.5$): as likely as getting heads when flipping a coin, i.e.,
 447 fifty-fifty
- 448 • Probable ($p = 1$ for calculation purposes): more likely to happen than not

449

450 The probability levels p represent the likelihood of an event happening, and will be
 451 used to calculate a final likelihood of an invasion to occur (see Figure 1 and Table 1).

452

453 Figure 1 illustrates how to calculate a final Likelihood score from the answers
 454 provided in LIK1-LIK6. Subsequently, this value can be transcribed into a Likelihood
 455 description as in Table 1, which feeds into the Risk assessment (Table 2).

456

457

458

459 **Figure 1 How to calculate Likelihood score**

460 This is based on LIK1–LIK6. The likelihood descriptions to extract a Risk score for the Risk
 461 assessment in Table 2 can then be found in Table 1.

462

463

464 **Table 1 Likelihoods in numbers and words**

465 Transcription of Likelihood scores into descriptions for the Risk score in Table 2. The Likelihood score
 466 is calculated as in Figure 1.

467

Likelihood score	Likelihood (description)
$p \leq 0.000001$	Extremely unlikely
$0.000001 < p \leq 0.0027$	Very unlikely
$0.0027 < p \leq 0.027$	Unlikely
$0.027 < p \leq 0.5$	Fairly probable
$p > 0.5$	Probable

468

469

470 **LIK1 Likelihood of entry via unaided primary pathways**

471 Estimate the probability that the *Taxon* enters the *Area* from outside the *Area* through unaided
472 pathways within the timespan of a decade. Consider all the unaided pathways mentioned under
473 BAC14. Features of the *Taxon* which favour unaided entry include presence in neighbouring countries
474 and regions, water or wind dispersed propagules (e.g. floating propagules), the ability to fly long
475 distances, the ability for fish to move from one river catchment where introduced, to another via
476 connected waterways. Animal dispersal is also considered here, except domestic and farm animals
477 which are included under LIK2. The following factors can aid entry via animals: edible parts (e.g.
478 fruits) which are eaten by animals, propagules with spines/barbs/sticky substances which can attach
479 to animals, very small propagules which can get stuck in fur and feathers, pests attached to plants or
480 animals. List the pathways and corresponding likelihoods in the comments section. In the response,
481 give the highest likelihood for any pathway. The assessment should be based on the likelihood of
482 entry based on current and future pathways.

483 If the *Taxon* is present in the *Area* (see BAC10), the probability of entry should be set as 1. Still fill in
484 this section as if the *Taxon* was not present and give details on pathways, as this can inform risk
485 management and the feasibility to stop future immigration. Start the rationale with “*The Taxon* is
486 currently present in the country and so the response is set to 1 as per the framework. In terms of the
487 likelihood of future introductions...”. However, for the calculations, use the probability of 1.
488 Provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2
489 and justify the level given in the Rationale.

490

491 **Response options:**

492 Extremely unlikely ($p = 0.000001$): the *Taxon* and its propagules are highly sessile and are known
493 never to disperse on its own – proof is required for inability to move, otherwise classify as “Very
494 unlikely”.

495 Very unlikely ($p = 0.0027$): the *Taxon* and its propagules are sessile and do not usually disperse on
496 their own

497 Unlikely ($p = 0.027$): the *Taxon* is sessile, but it can disperse during one specific life stage, dispersal
498 capabilities are slow and short distance

499 Fairly probable ($p = 0.5$): the *Taxon* is highly mobile during at least one of its life stages and can reach
500 a high dispersal capability during one of its life stages

501 Probable ($p = 1$): highly mobile *Taxon* with dispersal capability fast and over large distances

502 Present in the *Area* ($p = 1$): based on BAC10 the *Taxon* is already present and so the likelihood of
503 entry via unaided primary pathways should be set to one for the purposes of scoring risk, but
504 the potential for future introductions should still be scored.

505 Don't know ($p = 1$): no information is available on the unaided pathways available to the *Taxon*

506

507

508 **LIK2 Likelihood of entry via human aided primary pathways**

509 Estimate the probability that the *Taxon* enters the *Area* from outside the *Area* through the pathways
510 mentioned under BAC14 which are human mediated (as opposed to unaided, which are covered in
511 LIK1) within the timespan of a decade. This includes intentional and accidental (unintentional)
512 pathways. List the pathways and corresponding likelihoods in the comments section. This also
513 includes entry from neighbouring countries (consider it could in future be introduced into neighbouring
514 countries). In the response, give the highest likelihood for any pathway. The assessment should be
515 based on the likelihood of introductions based on current and future pathways. For taxa which are
516 already present in the *Area*, mainly focus on unintentional pathways.

517 If the *Taxon* is present in the *Area* (see BAC10), the probability of entry should be set as 1. Still fill in
518 this section as if the *Taxon* was not present and give details on pathways, as this can inform risk
519 management and the feasibility to stop future immigration. Start the rationale with “*The Taxon* is

520 currently present in the country and so the response is set to 1 as per the framework. In terms of the
521 likelihood of future introductions...". However, for the calculations, use the probability of 1.
522 Provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2
523 and justify the level given in the Rationale.

524
525 **Response options:**

526 Extremely unlikely ($p = 0.000001$): There is currently no human aided entry pathway available/in use
527 for the *Taxon*, and no future pathway is expected to arise
528 Very unlikely ($p = 0.0027$): There is currently a human aided entry pathway available/in use, but the
529 *Taxon* is highly sensitive to movement and is unlikely to arrive alive at any life stage
530 Unlikely ($p = 0.027$): There is a human aided entry pathway available/in use which is infrequently
531 used, and/or future new pathways are expected to arise; also, the *Taxon* is not expected to
532 arrive in high numbers
533 Fairly probable ($p = 0.5$): Several human aided entry pathways are available/in use but not regularly
534 used, and/or some potentially lead to a high number of introductions
535 Probable ($p = 1$): Several human aided entry pathways available and regularly used for the *Taxon*,
536 and high numbers of individuals expected.
537 Present in the *Area* ($p = 1$): based on BAC10 the *Taxon* is already present and so the likelihood of
538 entry via unaided primary pathways should be set to one for the purposes of scoring risk, but
539 the potential for future introductions should still be scored.
540 Don't know ($p = 1$): no information is available on the human aided pathways used by the *Taxon*

541
542

543 **LIK3 Habitat suitability**

544 Indicate the likelihood of the *Taxon* to find suitable habitats in the *Area* for survival and reproduction.
545 Assess here the biotic conditions needed for the *Taxon's* survival and/or reproduction. This includes
546 for example the presence of suitable food items, hosts, pollinators and seed dispersers. If the *Area*
547 encompasses multiple habitats, consider those that are most likely suited and mention in the
548 comments section which habitats were assessed. Thus, also take the habitat specificity of the *Taxon*
549 into account. Artificial habitats include for example (with increasing degree of artificiality) gardens,
550 zoos, greenhouses, indoor habitats.
551 Provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2
552 and justify the level given in the Rationale.

553
554 **Response options:**

555 Extremely unlikely ($p = 0.000001$): the *Taxon* is extremely specialised and there is no suitable habitat
556 in the *Area*, none of the key conditions for the *Taxon's* survival are met
557 Very unlikely ($p = 0.0027$): the *Taxon* is highly specialised, but there is reason to assume that it might
558 adapt to some biotic habitat conditions; only highly artificial habitats which are rare or difficult to
559 maintain are suitable.
560 Unlikely ($p = 0.027$): the *Area* provides habitat that is only partly suitable to the *Taxon*; certain artificial
561 habitats are suitable
562 Fairly probable ($p = 0.5$): the key conditions are met, but only in a marginal part of the *Area*; also non-
563 artificial habitats are suitable.
564 Probable ($p = 1$): all key biotic habitat conditions are met in a large part of the *Area*.
565 Don't know ($p = 1$): no information is available on habitat requirements of the *Taxon*

566
567

568 **LIK4 Climate suitability**

569 Indicate the likelihood of the *Taxon* to find suitable climate and other abiotic conditions (e.g., soil) in
570 the *Area* for survival and reproduction. Use the native and alien ranges as references for the *Taxon's*
571 distribution, as obtained in BAC7 and BAC8. As a minimal standard, use published maps of climate
572 zones to check whether the climate in the *Area* is suitable for the *Taxon*. Such maps include the
573 following:

- 574 - Koeppen-Geiger climate zones, updated by Peel et al. (2007)
575 - Richardson and Thuiller (2007) maps of global locations that match South African climates

576
577 Climate models are more desirable and lead to a higher confidence in the assessment.

578 If the *Area* encompasses multiple climate zones, consider those that are most likely suited and
579 mention in the comments section which climatic zones were assessed. For species already present in
580 the *Area*, the answer cannot be “extremely unlikely”.
581 Provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2
582 and justify the level given in the Rationale.

583

584 **Response options:**

585 Extremely unlikely ($p = 0.000001$): The *Area* provides no suitable climate (including artificially created
586 environments)

587 Very unlikely ($p = 0.0027$): The *Area* provides no suitable climate, but suitable climate can be
588 artificially created in small (<5%) parts of the *Area*.

589 Unlikely ($p = 0.027$): The *Area* provides little (<5%) climatic overlap with the known distribution of the
590 *Taxon*, excluding artificially created suitable habitats.

591 Fairly probable ($p = 0.5$): The main climatic requirements are met in a marginal (>5% but <20% - one
592 fifth) part of the *Area*.

593 Probable ($p = 1$): The main climatic requirements are met in a larger part (>20%) of the *Area*.

594 Don't know ($p = 1$): no information is available on the climatic requirements of the *Taxon*

595

596

597 **LIK5 Unaided secondary (dispersal) pathways**

598 This includes the unaided pathways currently or potentially bringing the *Taxon* from the occupied
599 regions to elsewhere within the *Area*. It excludes unaided pathways bringing propagules from areas
600 outside of the *Area* into the *Area* (covered in LIK1). Indicate the probability that the *Taxon* disperses
601 naturally from a population within the *Area* to currently unoccupied regions and habitats. Mention
602 details of the expected dispersal pathways and mechanisms in the comments section. More precisely,
603 try to estimate the probability that the *Taxon* can disperse > 50 km in a decade. Features of the *Taxon*
604 which favour unaided dispersal include water or wind dispersed propagules (e.g. floating propagules),
605 the ability to fly long distances, the ability for fish to move from one river catchment where introduced,
606 to another via connected waterways. Animal dispersal is also considered here, except domestic and
607 farm animals which are included under LIK6. The following factors can aid dispersal by animals:
608 edible parts (e.g. fruits) which are eaten by animals, propagules with spines/barbs/sticky substances
609 which can attach to animals, very small propagules which can get stuck in fur and feathers, pests
610 attached to plants or animals.

611 Provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2
612 and justify the level given in the Rationale.

613

614 **Response options:**

615 Extremely unlikely ($p = 0.000001$): the *Taxon* and its propagules (e.g., seeds, etc) or life cycle stages
616 are highly sessile and are known never to disperse on their own – proof is required for inability
617 to move, otherwise classify as “Very unlikely”.

618 Very unlikely ($p = 0.0027$): the *Taxon* and its propagules (e.g., seeds etc.) or life cycle stages are
619 sessile and do not usually disperse on their own

620 Unlikely ($p = 0.027$): the *Taxon* is sessile, but it can disperse during one specific life cycle stage (e.g.,
621 seeds etc.), dispersal capabilities are slow and short distance (< 50km in 10 years)

622 Fairly probable ($p = 0.5$): the *Taxon* is mobile and can reach a high dispersal capability during one of
623 of the stages of its life cycle (e.g., seeds etc.)

624 Probable ($p = 1$): highly mobile *Taxon* with the ability to disperse rapidly and over large distances

625 Don't know ($p = 1$): no information is available on unaided dispersal pathways used by the *Taxon*

626

627

628 **LIK6 Human aided secondary (dispersal) pathways**

629 This includes the human aided (intentional and accidental) pathways currently or potentially bringing
630 the *Taxon* from the occupied regions and habitats elsewhere within the *Area*. This question does not
631 include dispersal from outside of the *Area* to the *Area* as this is covered in LIK2. Indicate the
632 probability of the *Taxon* being dispersed from a population within the *Area* to uninvaded habitats.
633 Intentional and unintentional pathways need to be considered. Mention details of the expected
634 pathways in the comments section. The likelihood score relates to the proximity of the *Taxon* to
635 human and domestic/farm animals and frequency of contact, which allows it to be dispersed in these
636 kinds of dispersal pathways, as well as traits and features of the *Taxon* which facilitate for it to be
637 moved around.

638 More precisely, try to estimate the probability that human-mediated dispersal takes (propagules of)
639 the *Taxon* > 50 km in a decade.
640 Features of the *Taxon* which favour human aided dispersal include edible parts (e.g. fruits),
641 propagules with spines/barbs/sticky substances which can attach to clothing, vehicles and boats,
642 building materials, very small propagules which can get stuck in clothing/shoes or with movement of
643 ornamental plants and be transported unnoticed. Dispersal by domestic and farm animals is included
644 here.
645 Provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2
646 and justify the level given in the Rationale.
647

648 **Response options:**

649 Extremely unlikely ($p = 0.000001$): the *Taxon* is not present in places accessible by humans, domestic
650 and/or farm animals
651 Very unlikely ($p = 0.0027$): the *Taxon* is only present in places humans, domestic and/or farm animals
652 can reach with difficulty, and/or has no features which make it likely to be dispersed human
653 aided
654 Unlikely ($p = 0.027$): the *Taxon* is present in places where humans, domestic and/or farm animals
655 occasionally occur, and/or has features which make it possible to be dispersed human aided,
656 but only exceptional cases
657 Fairly probable ($p = 0.5$): the *Taxon* is present in places easily accessible by humans and/or it or its
658 propagules are easily moved, i.e. it possesses some feature mentioned above
659 Probable ($p = 1$): the *Taxon* is present in a place frequented by humans, and it or its propagules are
660 easily and regularly moved due to features mentioned above
661 Don't know ($p = 1$): no information is available on the human aided pathways used by the *Taxon*
662

663 **3. Consequences**

664

665 In this section, all evidence of impacts in the global alien range (including the *Area*)
 666 available for the *Taxon* needs to be collated and scored for environmental impacts
 667 and socio-economic impacts. Data on the impacts of the *Taxon* itself from the *Area*
 668 or other alien regions are the most desirable (CON1a-k) and CON2a-f)). Only if no
 669 data are available on the *Taxon* in any alien range globally should it be classified as
 670 Data Deficient (DD) under CON1 and CON2.

671 Additionally consider data in the native range of the *Taxon*, and/or estimate the
 672 magnitude of impact possible for the *Taxon* in the *Area* based on biological,
 673 ecological and behavioural traits in CON3. This needs to be filled in regardless of
 674 whether information on CON1 and CON2 is available, but can lead to similar
 675 responses if the impact of the *Taxon* has been well studied.

676 The environmental impact (CON1) is based on the Environmental Impact
 677 Classification for Alien Taxa (EICAT) system as adopted by the IUCN (IUCN 2020a,
 678 b) . EICAT classifies taxa into minimal concern (MC), minor (MN), moderate (MO),
 679 major (MR), massive (MV) according to the magnitude of impact they cause.

680 The socio-economic impact rating (CON2) is based partly on the Socio-Economic
 681 Impact Classification for Alien Taxa (SEICAT) by Bacher et al. (2018).

682 For a measure of future potential and currently unrecorded impact of the *Taxon* in
 683 the *Area*, CON3 includes considerations on the *Taxon*'s traits, behaviour and
 684 ecology and considers impacts recorded in the native range.

685

686 Fill all results as described below from CON1-3 into Figure 2 below and in the
 687 Reporting template to calculate maximum impact levels for the *Taxon*. For the
 688 consequence score, the maximum impact level should be taken between all the
 689 impact measures (CON1-3). This impact level is then used to calculate the risk score
 690 as described in Table 2.

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695 **Figure 2 How to calculate the Consequence score**

696 Schematic on how to derive the Consequence score for the risk assessment from all the questions in
 697 the Consequences sections (CON1–3).

698

699

700 **CON1 Environmental impact**

701 Fill in the Reporting template for each of the mechanisms as described below (CON1a-CON1k). Then
 702 use the scheme provided in Figure 2 to calculate the environmental impact score (CON1), which is
 703 the maximum of all the mechanisms. Report on the maximum impact found in any of the mechanisms
 704 for the global alien range in the Response for CON1 (except for CON1c), and the main mechanism

705 affected in the Rationale, but provide information on all the sectors and impact scores in CON1a)-
 706 CON1k), including detailed information on the references used for the assessments. If standardised
 707 impact assessments have been conducted previously for the *Taxon* and are available in the literature
 708 or published on the Global Invasive Species Database (www.iucngisd.org), information can be
 709 extracted from these assessments and no detailed search needs to be conducted.
 710 If no data on impact are available for the *Taxon* anywhere in the global alien range for any of the
 711 mechanisms described, mark the *Taxon* as Data Deficient (DD) here.

712

713 **CON1a Competition**

714 What is the evidence in the global alien range of the *Taxon* for impact through competition?
 715 Does the *Taxon* compete with native taxa for resources (e.g. food, water, space), leading to
 716 deleterious impact on native taxa somewhere in its global alien range?
 717 Classify the *Taxon* in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data are available or
 718 the mechanism is not applicable, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).
 719 Provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2
 720 and justify the level given in the Rationale.

721

722 **Response options:**

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)	Data Deficient (DD)
Competition resulting in replacement or local extinction of one or several native taxa; changes are irreversible	Competition resulting in local population extinction of at least one native taxon, but changes are reversible when the alien <i>Taxon</i> is no longer present	Competition resulting in a decline of population size of at least one native taxon, but no local population extinction	Competition affects performance of native individuals without decline of their populations	Negligible level of competition with native taxa; reduction of performance of native individuals is not detectable	No data are available to classify impact under this mechanism, or the mechanism is not applicable to the <i>Taxon</i>

723

724

725 **CON1b Predation**

726 This consists of the *Taxon* preying on native taxa somewhere in its global alien range, and includes
 727 direct effects leading to deleterious impact on native taxa. Note that this refers to the *Taxon* as a
 728 predator, not as prey.
 729 Classify the *Taxon* in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data are available or
 730 the mechanism is not applicable, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).
 731 Provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2
 732 and justify the level given in the Rationale.

733

734 **Response options:**

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)	Data Deficient (DD)
Predation results in local extinction of one or several native taxa; changes are irreversible	Predation results in local population extinction of at least one native taxon; reversible when the alien <i>Taxon</i> is no longer present	Predation results in a decline of population size of at least one native taxon, but no local population extinction	The alien <i>Taxon</i> preys on native taxa, without leading to a decline in their populations	Not applicable; predation on native taxa is classified at least as MN.	No data are available to classify impact under this mechanism, or the mechanism is not applicable to the <i>Taxon</i>

735

736

737 **CON1c Hybridisation**

738 This mechanism is handled slightly differently to the other CON mechanisms, as hybridisation is more
 739 context dependent than other mechanisms. For this mechanism, record if the *Taxon* hybridises with
 740 native species anywhere in its global alien range, leading to deleterious impact on native species.
 741 Classify the *Taxon* in an impact level according to the descriptions below and provide the data on the
 742 global hybridisation impact in the Rationale and provide relevant references. However, in the
 743 Response, consider if closely related species which the *Taxon* could hybridise with are present in the
 744 Area, and note the potential impact under this circumstance (note this can be lower than the global

745 hybridisation impact recorded). If no data are available or the mechanism is not applicable, the
 746 Response is Data Deficient (DD).
 747 Also note that this refers to impacts from hybridisation between alien and native species. Information
 748 on hybridisation between the *Taxon* and other alien species can be noted, but does not contribute to
 749 the scoring in the Response.
 750 Provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2
 751 and justify the level given in the Rationale.
 752
 753

Response options:

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)	Data Deficient (DD)
Hybridisation between the alien <i>Taxon</i> and native taxa leading to the loss of at least one pure native population (genomic extinction); pure native taxa cannot be recovered even if the alien and hybrids are no longer present	Hybridisation between the alien <i>Taxon</i> and native taxa leading to the loss of at least one pure native population (genomic extinction); reversible when the alien <i>Taxon</i> and hybrids are no longer present	Hybridisation between the alien <i>Taxon</i> and native taxa is regularly observed in the wild; local decline of populations of at least one pure native taxon, but pure native taxa persist	Hybridisation between the alien <i>Taxon</i> and native taxa is observed in the wild, but rare; no decline of pure local native populations	No hybridisation between the alien <i>Taxon</i> and native taxa observed in the wild (prezygotic barriers), hybridisation with a native taxon is possible in captivity	No data are available to classify impact under this mechanism, or the mechanism is not applicable to the <i>Taxon</i>

754

755

CON1d Transmission of disease

756 The *Taxon* transmits diseases to native species somewhere in its global alien range, leading to
 757 deleterious impact on native species.
 758 Classify the *Taxon* in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data are available or
 759 the mechanism is not applicable, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).
 760 Provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2
 761 and justify the level given in the Rationale.
 762
 763

Response options:

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)	Data Deficient (DD)
Transmission of disease to native taxa resulting in local extinction of at least one native taxon; changes are irreversible	Transmission of disease to native taxa resulting in local population extinction of at least one native taxon; reversible when the alien <i>Taxon</i> is no longer present	Transmission of disease to native taxa resulting in a decline of population size of at least one native taxon, but no local population extinction; disease is severely affecting native taxa, including mortality of individuals, and it has been found in native and alien co-occurring individuals (same time and space)	Transmission of disease to native taxa affects performance of native individuals without leading to a decline of their populations; alien <i>Taxon</i> is a host of a disease which has also been detected in native taxa and affects the performance of native taxa	The alien <i>Taxon</i> is a host or vector of a disease transmissible to native taxa but disease not detected in native taxa; reduction in performance of native individuals is not detectable	No data are available to classify impact under this mechanism, or the mechanism is not applicable to the <i>Taxon</i>

765

766

CON1e Parasitism

767 The *Taxon* parasitizes native species somewhere in its global alien range, leading directly or indirectly
 768 (e.g. through apparent competition) to deleterious impact on natives.
 769 Classify the *Taxon* in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data are available or
 770 the mechanism is not applicable, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).
 771

772 Provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2
 773 and justify the level given in the Rationale.

774
 775

Response options:

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)	Data Deficient (DD)
Parasites or pathogens directly result in local extinction of one or several native taxa; changes are irreversible	Parasites or pathogens directly result in local population extinction of at least one native taxon, but changes are reversible when the alien taxon is no longer present	Parasites or pathogens directly result in a decline of population size of at least one native taxon, but no local population extinction	Parasites or pathogens directly affect performance of native individuals without decline of their populations	Negligible level of parasitism or disease incidence (pathogens) on native taxa, reduction in performance of native individuals is not detectable	No data are available to classify impact under this mechanism, or the mechanism is not applicable to the <i>Taxon</i>

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 777

CON1f Poisoning/toxicity

779 The *Taxon* is toxic, or allergenic by ingestion somewhere in its global alien range, inhalation or
 780 contact to wildlife, or allelopathic to plants, leading to deleterious impact on native species.
 781 Classify the *Taxon* in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data are available or
 782 the mechanism is not applicable, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).
 783 Provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2
 784 and justify the level given in the Rationale.

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 786

Response options:

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)	Data Deficient (DD)
The alien <i>Taxon</i> is toxic/allergenic by ingestion, inhalation, or contact to wildlife or allelopathic to plants, resulting in local extinction of at least one native taxon; changes are irreversible	The alien <i>Taxon</i> is toxic/allergenic by ingestion, inhalation, or contact to wildlife or allelopathic to plants, resulting in local population extinction of at least one native taxon, but changes are reversible when the alien <i>Taxon</i> is removed	The alien <i>Taxon</i> is toxic/allergenic by ingestion, inhalation, or contact to wildlife or allelopathic to plants, resulting in a decline of population size of at least one native taxon, but no local population extinction	The alien <i>Taxon</i> is toxic/allergenic by ingestion, inhalation, or contact to wildlife or allelopathic to plants, affecting performance of native individuals without decline of their populations	The alien <i>Taxon</i> is toxic/allergenic/ allelopathic, but the level is very low, reduction of performance of native individuals is not detectable	No data are available to classify impact under this mechanism, or the mechanism is not applicable to the <i>Taxon</i>

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CON1g Bio-fouling or other direct physical disturbance

790 The accumulation of individuals of the *Taxon* on wetted surfaces (bio-fouling) or other direct physical
 791 disturbance not involved in a trophic interaction (e.g., trampling, rubbing, etc.) leads to deleterious
 792 impact on native species somewhere in its global alien range.
 793 Classify the *Taxon* in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data are available or
 794 the mechanism is not applicable, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).
 795 Provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2
 796 and justify the level given in the Rationale.

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 798

Response options:

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)	Data Deficient (DD)
Bio-fouling or other direct physical disturbance resulting in local extinction of one or several native	Bio-fouling or other direct physical disturbance resulting in local population extinction of at	Bio-fouling or other direct physical disturbance resulting in a decline of population size of	Bio-fouling or other direct physical disturbance affects performance of native individuals	Negligible level of bio-fouling or direct physical disturbance on native taxa; reduction in performance of	No data are available to classify impact under this mechanism, or the mechanism is

taxa; changes are irreversible	least one native taxon, but changes are reversible when the alien <i>Taxon</i> is no longer present	at least one native taxon, but no local population extinctions	without decline of their populations	native individuals is not detectable	not applicable to the <i>Taxon</i>
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CON1h Grazing/herbivory/browsing

Grazing, herbivory or browsing by the *Taxon* leads to deleterious impact on native plant species somewhere in its global alien range.

Classify the *Taxon* in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data are available or the mechanism is not applicable, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).

Provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2 and justify the level given in the Rationale.

Response options:

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)	Data Deficient (DD)
Herbivory/grazing /browsing resulting in local extinction of one or several native taxa; changes are irreversible	Herbivory/grazing /browsing resulting in local extinction of at least one native taxon, but changes are reversible when the alien <i>Taxon</i> is no longer present	Herbivory/grazing /browsing resulting in a decline of population size of at least one native taxon, but no local population extinction	Herbivory/grazing /browsing affects performance of individuals of native taxa without decline of their populations	Negligible level of herbivory/grazing /browsing on native taxa, reduction in performance of native taxa is not detectable	No data are available to classify impact under this mechanism, or the mechanism is not applicable to the <i>Taxon</i>

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CON1i Chemical, physical or structural impact on ecosystem

The *Taxon* causes changes to either: the chemical, physical, and/or structural biotope characteristics of the native environment; nutrient and/or water cycling; disturbance regimes; or natural succession, leading to deleterious impact on native species somewhere in the *Taxon*'s global alien range.

Classify the *Taxon* in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data are available or the mechanism is not applicable, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).

Provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2 and justify the level given in the Rationale.

Response options:

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)	Data Deficient (DD)
Changes in chemical, physical, and/or structural biotope characteristics; or changes in nutrient and water cycling; or disturbance regimes; or changes in natural succession, resulting in local extinction of at least one native taxon; changes are irreversible	Changes in chemical, physical, and/or structural biotope characteristics; or changes in nutrient cycling; or disturbance regimes; or changes in natural succession, resulting in local extinction of at least one native species, changes are reversible when the alien <i>Taxon</i> is no longer present	Changes in chemical, physical, and/or structural biotope characteristics; or changes in nutrient cycling; or disturbance regimes; or changes in natural succession, resulting in a decline of population size of at least one native taxon, but no local population extinction	Changes in chemical, physical, and/or structural biotope characteristics; or changes in nutrient cycling; or disturbance regimes; or changes in natural succession detectable, affecting performance (e.g., growth, reproduction, defence, immunocompetence) of native individuals without decline of their populations	Small changes in chemical, physical, and/or structural biotope characteristics; or changes in nutrient cycling; or disturbance regimes; or changes in natural succession detectable, but no reduction of performance of native individuals	No data are available to classify impact under this mechanism, or the mechanism is not applicable to the <i>Taxon</i>

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CON1k Indirect impacts through interactions with other species

The *Taxon* interacts with other (native or alien) taxa, (e.g., through pollination, seed dispersal, habitat modification, mesopredator release), facilitating deleterious impact on native species somewhere in its global alien range.

Classify the *Taxon* in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data are available or the mechanism is not applicable, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).

Provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2 and justify the level given in the Rationale.

Response options:

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)	Data Deficient (DD)
Interaction of an alien <i>Taxon</i> with other taxa leading to indirect impacts (e.g., pollination, seed dispersal, habitat modification, apparent competition) causing local extinction of one or several native taxa, leading to irreversible changes that would not have occurred in the absence of the alien <i>Taxon</i>	Interaction of an alien <i>Taxon</i> with other taxa leading to indirect impacts (e.g., pollination, seed dispersal, habitat modification, apparent competition) causing local extinction of at least one native taxon; changes are reversible but would not have occurred in the absence of the alien <i>Taxon</i>	Interaction of an alien <i>Taxon</i> with other taxa leading to indirect impacts (e.g., pollination, seed dispersal, habitat modification, apparent competition) causing a decline of population size of at least one native taxon, but no local population extinction; impacts would not have occurred in the absence of the alien <i>Taxon</i>	Interaction of an alien <i>Taxon</i> with other taxa leading to indirect impacts (e.g., pollination, seed dispersal, apparent competition) affecting performance of native individuals without decline of their populations; impacts would not have occurred in the absence of the alien <i>Taxon</i>	Interaction of an alien <i>Taxon</i> with other taxa leading to indirect impacts (e.g., pollination, seed dispersal, apparent competition) but reduction in performance of native individuals is not detectable	No data are available to classify impact under this mechanism, or the mechanism is not applicable to the <i>Taxon</i>

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CON2 Socio-economic impact

Assess the socio-economic impact of the *Taxon* in its global alien range (i.e. everywhere it has been introduced outside of its native range). Perform a SEICAT assessment on the *Taxon* as described in Bacher et al. 2018, and in CON2a) to CON2d) below. This concerns impacts on the following constituents of human well-being:

- (a) safety
- (b) material and immaterial assets
- (c) health
- (d) social, spiritual and cultural relations

Fill in the Reporting template for each of the constituents of human well-being (CON2a-CON2d), and use Figure 2 to calculate the overall socio-economic impact score. Report on the maximum impact found in any of the constituents of human well-being across the global alien range in the Response to CON2, and the main constituent affected in the Rationale, but provide information on all the constituents and impact scores in CON2a)-2d), including detailed information on the references used for the assessments.

If no data on impact are available for the *Taxon* in any part of its alien range globally on any of the constituents of human well-being described below, mark the *Taxon* as Data Deficient (DD) here and additionally fill in CON4.

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CON2a Safety

This concerns impacts on human well-being affecting activities related to safety, for example personal safety, secure resource access, security from disasters. Classify the *Taxon* in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data are available, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).

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861 Provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2
 862 and justify the level given in the Rationale.

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864 **Response options:**

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)	Data Deficient (DD)
Local disappearance of an activity from all or part of the area invaded by the alien <i>Taxon</i> affecting aspects of human safety. Change is likely to be permanent and irreversible for at least a decade after removal of the alien <i>Taxon</i> , due to fundamental structural changes of socio-economic community or environmental conditions ("regime shift")	Local disappearance of an activity from all or part of the area invaded by the alien <i>Taxon</i> affecting aspects of human safety. Collapse of the specific social activity, switch to other activities, or abandonment of activity without replacement, or emigration from region. Change is likely to be reversible within a decade after removal or control of the alien <i>Taxon</i> . "Local disappearance" does not necessarily imply the disappearance of activities from the entire region assessed, but refers to the typical spatial scale over which social communities in the region are characterised (e.g. a human settlement)	Negative effects on well-being leading to changes in activity size, fewer people participating in an activity, but the activity is still carried out. Reductions in activity size can be due to various reasons, e.g. moving the activity to regions without the alien <i>Taxon</i> or to other parts of the area less invaded by the alien <i>Taxon</i> ; partial abandonment of an activity without replacement by other activities; or switch to other activities while staying in the same area invaded by the alien <i>Taxon</i> . Also, spatial displacement, abandonment or switch of activities does not increase human well-being compared to levels before the alien <i>Taxon</i> invaded the region (no increase in opportunities due to the alien <i>Taxon</i>)	Negative effect on peoples' well-being, such that the alien <i>Taxon</i> makes it difficult for people to participate in their normal activities. Individual people in an activity suffer regarding safety. Reductions of well-being can be detected through e.g. income loss, health problems, higher effort or expenses to participate in activities, increased difficulty in accessing goods, disruption of social activities, induction of fear, but no change in activity size is reported, i.e. the number of people participating in that activity remains the same	No deleterious impacts reported despite availability of relevant studies with regard to its impact on human well-being. Taxa that have been evaluated under the SEICAT process but for which impacts have not been assessed in any study should not be classified in this category, but rather should be classified as data deficient	There is no information to classify the <i>Taxon</i> with respect to its impact, or insufficient time has elapsed since introduction for impacts to have become apparent

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867 **CON2b Material and immaterial assets**

868 This concerns impacts on human well-being affecting activities leading to changes in the availability
 869 and quality of material and immaterial assets, for example adequate livelihoods, sufficient nutritious
 870 food, shelter, access to goods. Classify the *Taxon* in an impact level according to the descriptions
 871 below. If no data are available, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).

872 Provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2
 873 and justify the level given in the Rationale.

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875 **Response options:**

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)	Data Deficient (DD)
Local disappearance of an activity from all or part of the area invaded by the alien <i>Taxon</i> . Change is likely to be permanent and irreversible for at least a decade after removal of the alien <i>Taxon</i> , due to fundamental structural changes of socio-economic community or environmental conditions ("regime shift")	Local disappearance of an activity from all or part of the area invaded by the alien <i>Taxon</i> . Collapse of the specific social activity, switch to other activities, or abandonment of activity without replacement, or emigration from region. Change is likely to be reversible within a decade after removal or control of the alien <i>Taxon</i> . "Local disappearance" does not necessarily imply the disappearance of activities from the entire region assessed, but refers to the typical spatial scale over which social communities in the region are characterised (e.g. a human settlement)	Negative effects on well-being leading to changes in activity size, fewer people participating in an activity, but the activity is still carried out. Reductions in activity size can be due to various reasons, e.g. moving the activity to regions without the alien <i>Taxon</i> or to other parts of the area less invaded by the alien <i>Taxon</i> ; partial abandonment of an activity without replacement by other activities; or switch to other activities while staying in the same area invaded by the alien <i>Taxon</i> . Also, spatial displacement, abandonment or switch of activities does not increase human well-being compared to levels before the alien <i>Taxon</i> invaded the region (no increase in opportunities due to the alien <i>taxon</i>)	Negative effect on peoples' well-being, such that the alien <i>Taxon</i> makes it difficult for people to participate in their normal activities. Individual people in an activity suffer in at least one constituent of well-being (i.e. security; material and non-material assets; health; social, spiritual and cultural relations). Reductions of well-being can be detected through e.g. income loss, health problems, higher effort or expenses to participate in activities, increased difficulty in accessing goods, disruption of social activities, induction of fear, but no change in activity size is reported, i.e. the number of people participating in that activity remains the same	No deleterious impacts reported despite availability of relevant studies with regard to its impact on human well-being. Taxa that have been evaluated under the SEICAT process but for which impacts have not been assessed in any study should not be classified in this category, but rather should be classified as data deficient	There is no information to classify the <i>Taxon</i> with respect to its impact, or insufficient time has elapsed since introduction for impacts to have become apparent

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878 **CON2c Health**

879 This includes impacts on human well-being affecting their health, including strength, feeling well,
880 access to clean air and water. Classify the *Taxon* in an impact level according to the descriptions
881 below. If no data are available, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).

882 Provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2
883 and justify the level given in the Rationale.

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885 **Response options:**

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)	Data Deficient (DD)
Local disappearance of an activity from all or part of the area invaded by the alien <i>Taxon</i> . Change is likely to be	Local disappearance of an activity from all or part of the area invaded by the alien <i>Taxon</i> . Collapse of the specific	Negative effects on well-being leading to changes in activity size, fewer people participating in an activity, but	Negative effect on peoples' well-being, such that the alien <i>taxon</i> makes it difficult for people to participate in	No deleterious impacts reported despite availability of relevant studies regarding its impact on human well-being. Taxa that have been	There is no information to classify the <i>Taxon</i> with respect to its impact, or insufficient time has elapsed since

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)	Data Deficient (DD)
permanent and irreversible for at least a decade after removal of the alien <i>Taxon</i> , due to fundamental structural changes of socio-economic community or environmental conditions ("regime shift")	social activity, switch to other activities, or abandonment of activity without replacement, or emigration from region. Change is likely to be reversible within a decade after removal or control of the alien <i>Taxon</i> . "Local disappearance" does not necessarily imply the disappearance of activities from the entire region assessed, but refers to the typical spatial scale over which social communities in the region are characterised (e.g. a human settlement)	the activity is still carried out. Reductions in activity size can be due to various reasons, e.g. moving the activity to regions without the alien <i>Taxon</i> or to other parts of the area less invaded by the alien <i>Taxon</i> ; partial abandonment of an activity without replacement by other activities; or switch to other activities while staying in the same area invaded by the alien <i>Taxon</i> . Also, spatial displacement, abandonment or switch of activities does not increase human well-being compared to levels before the alien <i>Taxon</i> invaded the region (no increase in opportunities due to the alien <i>Taxon</i>)	their normal activities. Individual people in an activity suffer in at least one constituent of well-being (i.e. security; material and non-material assets; health; social, spiritual and cultural relations). Reductions of well-being can be detected through e.g. income loss, health problems, higher effort or expenses to participate in activities, increased difficulty in accessing goods, disruption of social activities, induction of fear, but no change in activity size is reported, i.e. the number of people participating in that activity remains the same	evaluated under the SEICAT process but for which impacts have not been assessed in any study should not be classified in this category, but rather should be classified as data deficient	introduction for impacts to have become apparent

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CON2d Social, spiritual and cultural relations

This concerns impacts on human well-being affecting social, spiritual and cultural relations, for example social, spiritual and cultural practice, mutual respect, friendship. Classify the *Taxon* in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data are available, the Response is Data Deficient (DD). Provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2 and justify the level given in the Rationale.

Response options:

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)	Data Deficient (DD)
Local disappearance of an activity from all or part of the area invaded by the alien <i>Taxon</i> . Change is likely to be permanent and irreversible for at least a decade after removal of the alien <i>Taxon</i> , due to fundamental structural	Local disappearance of an activity from all or part of the area invaded by the alien <i>Taxon</i> . Collapse of the specific social activity, switch to other activities, or abandonment of activity without replacement, or emigration from	Negative effects on well-being leading to changes in activity size, fewer people participating in an activity, but the activity is still carried out. Reductions in activity size can be due to various reasons, e.g. moving the activity	Negative effect on peoples' well-being, such that the alien <i>Taxon</i> makes it difficult for people to participate in their normal activities. Individual people in an activity suffer in at least one constituent of well-being (i.e.	No deleterious impacts reported despite availability of relevant studies with regard to its impact on human well-being. Taxa that have been evaluated under the SEICAT process but for which impacts have not been assessed in any study should not	There is no information to classify the <i>Taxon</i> with respect to its impact, or insufficient time has elapsed since introduction for impacts to have become apparent

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)	Data Deficient (DD)
changes of socio-economic community or environmental conditions ("regime shift")	region. Change is likely to be reversible within a decade after removal or control of the alien <i>Taxon</i> . "Local disappearance" does not necessarily imply the disappearance of activities from the entire region assessed, but refers to the typical spatial scale over which social communities in the region are characterised (e.g. a human settlement)	to regions without the alien <i>Taxon</i> or to other parts of the area less invaded by the alien <i>Taxon</i> ; partial abandonment of an activity without replacement by other activities; or switch to other activities while staying in the same area invaded by the alien <i>Taxon</i> . Also, spatial displacement, abandonment or switch of activities does not increase human well-being compared to levels before the alien <i>Taxon</i> invaded the region (no increase in opportunities due to the alien <i>Taxon</i>)	security; material and non-material assets; health; social, spiritual and cultural relations). Reductions of well-being can be detected through e.g. income loss, health problems, higher effort or expenses to participate in activities, increased difficulty in accessing goods, disruption of social activities, induction of fear, but no change in activity size is reported, i.e. the number of people participating in that activity remains the same	be classified in this category, but rather should be classified as data deficient	

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898 **CON3 Potential impact**

899 This is filled in regardless of whether information on the other impact questions (CON1 and CON2) is
900 available. Information should be complementary/ additional to the evidence provided in CON1 and
901 CON2, and not repeat it. If you find you were using words like "might", "could", "potentially", etc. in
902 CON1 and CON2, this information should probably be presented here rather. Furthermore, use data
903 from the native range of the *Taxon* (e.g. impacts on agriculture) and/or estimate the magnitude of
904 impact possible if the *Taxon* were to be invasive in the *Area* based on its life history traits and trait
905 based models for similar taxa. For some taxa, it has been shown that species closely related with
906 similar ecological and behavioural strategies to alien species that cause high impacts are more prone
907 to cause negative impacts. Therefore, you can also include data of congeners or other closely related
908 species with similar life history traits here, but note which species were included and why. Specifically
909 consider the life history traits of the *Taxon* which could lead to impact, including undesirable traits, as
910 well as the recipient systems, meaning the recipient habitat and community. Undesirable traits include
911 (but do not exclusively consist of): produces spines, thorns or burrs, allelopathic, parasitic,
912 unpalatable to grazing animals, toxic to animals, host for recognised pests and pathogens, causes
913 allergies or is otherwise toxic to humans, creates a fire hazard in natural ecosystems, grows on
914 infertile soils, shade tolerant plant at some stage of its life cycle. Also consider here feeding habits,
915 novelty aspects, functional traits, and studies performed on other groups and taxa considering trait-
916 impact relationships.
917 In detail, estimate the potential of the *Taxon* to cause any impact in the magnitudes as described
918 under CON1 and CON2 in the *Area*, including impacts for which no evidence has been recorded yet.
919 Assume the *Taxon* is established and abundant in the *Area*, and consider the highest impact possible
920 under any of the mechanisms and to any sector.
921 Provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2
922 and justify the level given in the Rationale.
923

Response options	Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)
Environmental impact	Causes local extinction of at least one native taxon (i.e., taxa vanish from communities at sites where they occurred before the alien arrived), which is irreversible; even if the alien taxon is no longer present the native taxon cannot recolonize the area	Causes local or sub-population extinction of at least one native taxon (i.e., taxa vanish from communities at sites where they occurred before the alien arrived); which is reversible if the alien taxon is no longer present	Causes population declines in at least one native taxon, but no local population extinctions	Causes reductions in individual performance (e.g., growth, reproduction, defence, immunocompetence), but no declines in local native population sizes	Negligible level of impacts; no reduction in performance (e.g., growth, reproduction, defence, immunocompetence) of individuals of native taxa
Socio-economic impact	Local disappearance of an activity from all or part of the area invaded by the alien taxon. Change is likely to be permanent and irreversible for at least a decade after removal of the alien taxon, due to fundamental structural changes of socio-economic community or environmental conditions ("regime shift")	Local disappearance of an activity from all or part of the area invaded by the alien taxon. Collapse of the specific social activity, switch to other activities, or abandonment of activity without replacement, or emigration from region. Change is likely to be reversible within a decade after removal or control of the alien taxon.	Negative effects on well-being leading to changes in activity size, fewer people participating in an activity, but the activity is still carried out.	Negative effect on peoples' well-being, such that the alien taxon makes it difficult for people to participate in their normal activities. Individual people suffer in at least one constituent of well-being (i.e. security; material and non-material assets; health; social, spiritual and cultural relations).	No deleterious impacts reported despite availability of relevant studies with regard to its impact on human well-being
Potential impact	The <i>Taxon</i> is a transformer in its native range, has ecosystem engineering properties, or possesses other traits which suggest irreversible impacts on the community composition in the <i>Area</i> to occur. The <i>Taxon</i> is a pest of agricultural production in the native range and has the potential to cause irreversible losses of activities.	The <i>Taxon</i> has traits which suggest major impacts on native communities in the <i>Area</i> , but these impacts are likely to be reversible. The <i>Taxon</i> has traits which can lead to losses of activities.	The <i>Taxon</i> possesses several undesirable traits. Due to the traits of the <i>Taxon</i> and/or its behavior, it is expected to reduce population sizes of at least one native species, and/or human well-being leading to people changing their activities.	The <i>Taxon</i> does not possess any traits which could lead to effects on native species population sizes, but reduction in native individuals' performance is expected; and/or it could lead to loss in individual peoples' well-being and increased difficulties to perform normal activities. No changes to activity sizes.	Due to the traits of the <i>Taxon</i> no effect on native individuals' performance is expected. No effects on human well-being are expected. The <i>Taxon</i> does not possess any undesirable traits.

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4. Risk assessment calculations

The risk posed by an alien *Taxon* is the likelihood the *Taxon* will become an invader and the consequences in terms of impact resulting from the introduction of the *Taxon*. The Likelihood for the risk assessment is derived from LIK1-LIK6 as described in Figure 1 and Table 1. The Consequence score is derived from CON1-CON3, as summarised in Figure 2. Table 2 summarises how risk scores are derived from Consequence and Likelihood.

Table 2 Table to derive risk score from Likelihood and Consequences sections

		Consequence				
		MC	MN	MO	MR	MV
Likelihood	Extremely unlikely	low	low	low	medium	medium
	Very unlikely	low	low	low	medium	high
	Unlikely	low	low	medium	high	high
	Fairly probable	medium	medium	high	high	high
	Probable	medium	high	high	high	high

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The Risk assessment provides the evidence base for or against the listing of a *Taxon* under the NEMBA A&IS Regulations, whereas the Risk management section helps to decide which listing category is most suitable given the evidence available (Figure 3).

5. Management

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A decision on the listing *status*, i.e., whether a taxon should be listed as prohibited, Category 1a, 1b, or 2, and whether exemptions and prohibitions should be implemented, as outlined in the NEM:BA A&IS Regulations, is not only based on scientific evidence of risks, but also the value of the *Taxon*, and inherent features which influences the difficulty of control. Therefore, risk management considerations describing whether and how risks can be managed apply. This includes an evaluation of benefits and potential options available to reduce risks, including available biocontrol and its effectiveness.

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MAN1 What is the feasibility to stop future immigration?

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If the *Taxon* is not (yet) present in the *Area* (see BAC10), assess if future immigration of the *Taxon* into the *Area* can be prevented. This determines whether prevention is a feasible goal, if an emergency response plan is needed, and whether the *Taxon* should be added to a watch list (Figure 3). Based on the pathways identified in BAC14 and the answers provided in LIK1 and LIK2, estimate the feasibility to stop the *Taxon* from entering the *Area*. Provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2 and justify the level given in the Rationale.

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High: The *Taxon* is only introduced into the *Area* intentionally with pathways which are easy to regulate and control.
Low: The *Taxon* is also introduced into the *Area* unintentionally, for example as contaminant and stowaway, and/or is present in neighbouring countries and areas and is entering the *Area* unaided.

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971 **MAN2 Benefits of the Taxon**

972 This section (MAN2a & MAN2b) aims to highlight potential conflicts of interest and the potential need
973 for permitting or exemptions. If relevant, mention potential benefits here, but clearly separate the two,
974 and base your response on actual, current benefits in the *Area*. Capture each benefit and its
975 considered magnitude (high or low), whether it is currently realised in the *Area*, the potential for
976 replacing the benefits (for example using non-harmful alien or native taxa), and the stakeholders
977 benefitting from the service provided by the *Taxon*. Examples of stakeholders include academics,
978 agricultural sector, aquaculture sector, collectors, fishermen, food industry, forestry sector, general
979 public, land owners, landscapers, managers and policy makers, Non-Governmental Organisations,
980 nursery owners and plant wholesalers, pet shop owners, recreational ocean users, state agencies
981 (Novoa et al. 2018).

982 Provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2
983 and justify the level given in the Rationale.

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985 **MAN2a Socio-economic benefits of the Taxon**

986 Realised and current socio-economic benefits of the *Taxon* in the *Area* should be described to ensure
987 objectivity and recognition of the services that may be provided by the *Taxon*. In the Reporting
988 template, list all benefits of the *Taxon*, the magnitude as per the response options below, whether it is
989 a current and realised benefit (Current = Yes) or a potential impact (Current = No). Furthermore,
990 provide a rationale for whether the benefit can be replaced by other (e.g., non-harmful alien or native)
991 taxa, and list the stakeholders benefitting.

992 Include here if the *Taxon* is used for any of the following: fishing, gathering, logging, terrestrial animal
993 harvesting, in ceremony or ritual, for decorative or aesthetic purposes (e.g. as pets or ornamentals),
994 for energy, food, feed or fodder, learning and education, as materials for construction, as medicine or
995 for hygiene purposes, for recreation, or other uses (based on IPBES 2022).

996 . Benefits are rated as of high or low significance, based on the criteria outlined below. Details of the
997 benefits and why they are rated in the respective level need to be provided in the Rationale. If
998 applicable, mention potential benefits here (e.g., from different alien ranges, or as found in the native
999 range), but note those in the column “Current” as No.

1000 If the *Taxon* is listed as category 2, note the number of permits that have been issued for it (excluding
1001 permits issues for research, biocontrol, or display purposes as these are not always indicative of
1002 benefits, in many cases such permits are issued to develop better control methods). For this
1003 information go to <https://zenodo.org/record/8229321> and find the latest version of the permit
1004 database. The recommended citation will be specified available on Zenodo, e.g., SANBI, (2023).

1005 Provide a confidence level for each row based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material,
1006 Appendix S2 and justify the level given in the Rationale.

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1008 **Magnitude response options:**

1009 High: Significant benefits are expected if the *Taxon* provides a service or makes an activity possible
1010 which is not available without the *Taxon*, i.e., which is not provided by the native species in the
1011 *Area*. Also covered here are services provided by the *Taxon* which are essential for security,
1012 adequate livelihoods, sufficient nutritious food, access to clean air and water, and food.

1013 Low: List benefits which can relatively easily be replaced by another (native or non-harmful alien)
1014 taxon. Also covered here are services provided by the *Taxon* which affect aspects of human well-
1015 being related to social, spiritual and cultural relations, for example friendship and spiritual
1016 practices.

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1018 **MAN2b Environmental benefits of the Taxon**

1019 Here, benefits to the natural environment and native species in the *Area* are assessed. Benefits are
1020 rated as of high or low, based on the criteria outlined below. In the Reporting template, list all benefits
1021 of the *Taxon*, the magnitude as per the response options below, whether it is a current and realised
1022 benefit (Current = Yes) or a potential impact (Current = No). Furthermore, provide a rationale for
1023 whether the benefit can be replaced by other (non harmful alien or native) taxa, and list the
1024 stakeholders benefitting.

1025 Details of the benefits and why they are rated in the respective level need to be provided in the
1026 Rationale. If applicable, mention potential benefits here (e.g. from different alien ranges, or as found
1027 in the native range), but note those in the column “Current” as No.

1028 Provide a confidence level for each row based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material,
1029 Appendix S2 and justify the level given in the Rationale.

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1031 **Magnitude response options:**

1032 High: High benefits are expected if the *Taxon* provides a crucial habitat or food source to an
1033 environment. These functions might be replaceable over time by native taxa, but it indicates that
1034 current control would be detrimental to conservation or ecosystem functioning. Significant benefits
1035 are also noted if the *Taxon* provides resources to native species which are not or no longer
1036 available without the *Taxon* present, especially to rare, endemic or threatened species.

1037 Low: Benefits to native species and ecosystems which can relatively easily be replaced by another
1038 (native or non-harmful alien) taxon.

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1041 **MAN3 Can the risk be reduced?**

1042 Assess the feasibility of prohibitions, exemptions or permits to reduce the risk of the *Taxon* to an
1043 acceptable level while conserving the benefits listed in MAN2, if applicable. This question is split into
1044 four sections based on context: a) entities of the *Taxon*, b) environmental context, c) containment
1045 options, d) management options to reduce invasions if they happen. If the answer to any of the sub-
1046 questions is yes, the response here is set as yes.

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1048 **Response options:**

1049 Yes: Based on the responses given in MAN3a-d, the risk of the *Taxon* can be reduced to an
1050 acceptable level if permits are issued under certain conditions or if certain prohibitions or
1051 exemptions are adhered to.

1052 No: Based on the responses given in MAN3a-d, permitting is likely ineffective. Prohibitions and/or
1053 exemptions cannot practically be implemented to reduce the risk of the *Taxon*.

1054

1055

1056 **MAN3a Do some entities of the Taxon pose a reduced risk?**

1057 Assess here if certain entities of the *Taxon* pose a reduced risk. This might include varieties, cultivars
1058 or breeds which pose a reduced risk due to particular traits that the poses the reduce the potential for
1059 invasions and/or impact (e.g., reduced dispersal, reduced reproduction, e.g., sterility, or reduced
1060 defence from natural enemies). In the Rationale, justify the response and outline if this only applies
1061 under specific conditions (e.g., only if one sex of the *Taxon* is introduced).

1062 Provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2
1063 and justify the level given in the Rationale.

1064

1065 **Response options:**

1066 Yes: Some entities of the *Taxon* pose a reduced and acceptable risk and could be considered for
1067 exemption.

1068 No: All entities of the *Taxon* pose a similar risk.

1069

1070

1071 **MAN3b Is the risk of the Taxon reduced under certain environmental
1072 conditions?**

1073 Describe here if the risk of the *Taxon* is lower under certain environmental conditions in the *Area*. An
1074 example would be planting trees far from watercourses if they mainly spread with water. Such
1075 conditions could be used as permit conditions or form the basis for exemptions or prohibitions
1076 (prohibition would be based on preventing use in contexts where the risk is higher).

1077 Provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2
1078 and justify the level given in the Rationale.

1079

1080 **Response options:**

1081 Yes: Certain environmental conditions in the *Area* are unsuitable for the *Taxon* and it poses an
1082 acceptable risk there which could be considered under permit conditions or exemptions or
1083 prohibitions.

1084 No: Permitting under specific environmental conditions is likely ineffective for the *Taxon*.

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MAN3c Can containment options reduce the risk of the Taxon?

Describe in the Rationale which containment options could effectively reduce the risk of the *Taxon* to an acceptable level while keeping the benefits if implemented for permitting. This can include for example keeping pets in certain enclosures, allowing fish only in dams which do not connect to rivers, etc.

Provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2 and justify the level given in the Rationale.

Response options:

Yes: The issuing of permits under certain containment conditions can reduce the risk of the *Taxon* to an acceptable level.

No: Permitting is likely ineffective.

MAN3d Is management in place that can reduce the risk of invasion or impact of the Taxon?

Several invasive taxa have been brought under control through biological control, and similarly other management might be in place and is likely to continue regardless of how the *Taxon* is regulated. This question therefore assesses if there is management in place that can reduce the impact or invasion risk of the *Taxon* to an acceptable level so that active management becomes unnecessary. Provide details in the Rationale, including which biocontrol agents are available, if any, and their effectiveness in the *Area*. This assessment is based on the reduction in alternative control methods required.

Distinguish between the following in the Rationale, as per Klein (2011):

Complete: no other control measures are needed to reduce the *Taxon* to acceptable levels, at least at the sites where the agents are established in the *Area*.

Substantial: other methods are needed to reduce the *Taxon* to acceptable levels, but less effort is required (e.g., less frequent herbicide applications or less herbicide needed per unit area).

Negligible: in spite of damage inflicted by the agents, control of the *Taxon* remains entirely reliant on the implementation of other control measures.

Not determined: either the release of the agents has been too recent for meaningful evaluation, or the programme has not been evaluated.

Under investigation: the *Taxon* is currently under investigation for biocontrol in the *Area*, or agents are available for other regions, but no agent is yet approved/available for the *Area*.

Not available: no biocontrol agent is currently used for the *Taxon* in the *Area*.

The Response is based on the information required above, and distinguishes between taxa which are under complete control, and taxa under the other categories.

Provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2 and justify the level given in the Rationale.

Response options:

Yes: At least one biocontrol agent is available for the *Taxon*, and it (or the combination of several agents) leads to complete control of the *Taxon* so that no other control measures are necessary to reduce the invasion of the *Taxon* in the *Area*.

No: No biocontrol agent or combination of agents used for the *Taxon* is currently fully effective in the *Area*; or there is currently no biocontrol available for the *Taxon* in the *Area*.

MAN4 Should eradication be considered as a management goal?

This question aims to evaluate if eradication should be considered as a potential management goal. It is answered based on the status of the *Taxon* in the *Area* currently, not where it could be found. This information does not replace a management feasibility study.

Given there is often a short temporal window during which eradication is feasible (and after which the *Taxon* has become too widespread and numerous in the *Area*) it is important that control efforts are not delayed until a regulatory decision has been finalised. Therefore, under this framework, a recommendation can be based on a full evaluation of the feasibility of eradication, and on a preliminary evaluation. If the evaluation is preliminary the recommendation should be temporary and re-evaluated pending data on any ongoing eradication attempts and the completion of an eradication

1144 feasibility study. If the pilot management achieves eradication before formal regulatory confirmation of
1145 an eradication attempt, then it will in no way limit future options or delay eradication until it is too late.
1146 However, if no eradication feasibility study has been done, the *Taxon* should only be conditionally
1147 listed as 1a, and re-evaluated in five years.
1148 Indicate one of the response options in the Response field of the Reporting template, and justify your
1149 answer in the Rationale, providing suitable references.
1150 Provide a confidence level based on the guidelines given in the Supplementary Material, Appendix S2
1151 and justify the level given in the Rationale.
1152

1153 **Response options:**

1154 Yes (confirmed by an eradication feasibility study): An eradication feasibility study has been
1155 conducted in the *Area* showing the *Taxon* is a suitable eradication target;

1156 Yes (an eradication feasibility study has not yet been finalised): the distribution of the *Taxon* is very
1157 limited (a few populations); populations are easily accessible; eradication trials are currently
1158 undertaken; other aspects of the populations in the *Area* make the *Taxon* a potential eradication
1159 target.

1160 No: The *Taxon* is widespread in the *Area*; and/or many populations of the *Taxon* are present; or it is
1161 generally difficult to manage (e.g. difficult to detect or distinguish from native species, specialist
1162 equipment or techniques are required / multiple approaches are needed for control to be effective /
1163 management is an expensive operation over several seasons)
1164
1165

1166 **6. Recommendations and reporting**

1167 Based on the information in the risk assessment and risk management sections,
1168 several broad recommendations for the regulation of an alien *Taxon* are considered
1169 (Figure 3). These differ based on whether the *Taxon* is already present in the *Area*,
1170 whether prevention or eradication are feasible management goals, and whether the
1171 risk of the *Taxon* can be reduced under certain conditions which might warrant using
1172 it under permit in certain conditions (Figure 3). Figure 3 describes how to determine
1173 the recommendations for Risk management and listing from the answers provided in
1174 the Risk analysis. In the last question, outline the options for regulation justifying the
1175 with information provided in the risk analysis.
1176

1177 **REC1 What are the options for regulation of the *Taxon*?**

1178 Based on the information provided in the risk analysis and the decision tree in Figure 3, details of the
1179 considerations for the possible options for listing need to be provided, which should be structured into
1180 the following sections: Options for regulation, Rationale, Recommendation, and References. This is
1181 intended to support those tasked with decision making, so a critical evaluation of options (including
1182 those that are not suitable) backed up by evidence can be made. Also describe here if it is
1183 recommended to deviate from the options provided by the decision tree in Figure 3, and provide a
1184 rationale. Especially consider if the *Taxon* has significant benefits and if conflicts of interest are
1185 expected for potential listing under category 2.

1186 Furthermore, following on from MAN4, this section assesses if certain entities of the *Taxon* should be
1187 regulated differently or separately and if so, how.

1188 Also note here if the *Taxon* should be prioritised for re-evaluation within a certain timeframe (e.g., 5
1189 years). This is relevant if there is high uncertainty about certain aspects of the risk analysis which can
1190 influence the listing recommendation and could be cleared up with more research. These specifically
1191 refer to the following:

- 1192 - Taxonomic uncertainties
 - 1193 - Presence of the *Taxon* in the country
 - 1194 - The importance of the *Taxon* for an industry
- 1195
1196

1197 For an easily digestible overview of the analysis, a summary sheet including the
1198 conclusions from each table needs to be provided, with short descriptions on the risk
1199 of the *Taxon*, benefits, and management considerations. The full risk analysis with

1200 each question answered and all references, including detailed information on
 1201 assessors, reviewers, *Taxon* and *Area*, and maps should be provided as well.
 1202
 1203

1204
 1205 **Figure 3** A decision tree for determining the appropriate regulatory category and risk
 1206 management response.

1207 The listing categories (1a, 1b, 2) are as per South Africa's NEM:BA A&IS Regulations. This decision
 1208 tree should serve as a guideline for recommending the appropriate listing category, but other relevant
 1209 information from the risk analysis should be considered to develop the recommendations if needed.
 1210 This particularly refers to the benefits of a *Taxon* (or the lack thereof) and the potential for conflicts
 1211 with stakeholders.

1212
 1213

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1268 **Supplementary Material**
1269 **Appendix S1 Glossary**

1270

1271 **NEM:BA A&IS Regulations:** The National Environmental Management: Biodiversity Act
1272 (NEM:BA, Act 10 of 2004) Alien and Invasive Species Regulations (Department of
1273 Environmental Affairs 2014)

1274 **Alien taxon:** A taxon in a given area whose presence there is due to intentional or
1275 accidental introduction as a result of human activity. Taxa that have part of their native
1276 range in a given country, but whose presence in another part of the same country is
1277 attributable to human actions that enabled the taxon to overcome fundamental
1278 biogeographical barriers, are also referred to as alien here.

1279 **Area:** The area of assessment for the risk analysis. Specify the geographic entity under
1280 consideration, i.e. the geographic scope of the assessment. In most cases this will be
1281 the whole of South Africa, but can also be only a part of the country, for example a
1282 single province, a national park or a river catchment. The region under assessment will
1283 be referred to as the Area in the framework.

1284 **Extralimital:** A taxon that has part of their native range in a given area, but whose presence
1285 in another part of the same area is attributable to human actions that enabled the taxon
1286 to naturally disperse to the new part of the area

1287 **Invasive taxon:** A taxon which is alien to an area and which has self-sustaining populations
1288 there with propagules spreading from the initial site of introduction.

1289 **Native-alien population:** a population that resulted from the human-mediated dispersal of
1290 individuals of a taxon beyond a biogeographical barrier to a point beyond that taxon's
1291 native range, but that is still within the same area (political entity) as parts of the taxon's
1292 native range.

1293 **Pathway:** The processes by which taxa are moved between areas.

1294 **Primary (introduction) pathway:** The combined processes by which taxa are introduced
1295 from one geographical location to another (cf. Vector). Classified into categories and sub-
1296 categories.

1297 **Propagule:** any stage in the life cycle of an organisms, for example spore, seed, fruit, larval
1298 stage, fragment, or other part of an organism capable of reproduction by sexual or asexual
1299 means

1300 **Secondary (dispersal) pathway:** The processes by which taxa disperse or are dispersed
1301 from one area of introduction to another.

1302 **Sessile:** those plants which are attached directly by the base without a stalk or peduncle; for
1303 animals those that are fixed in one place or immobile, e.g. barnacles, corals, etc.

1304 **Risk analysis:** The process of identifying and assessing the likelihood and consequence of
1305 an event, as well as considerations as to manage and communicate the risks.

1306 **Risk assessment:** The process of evaluating the likelihood and consequence of an event
1307 taking place. In this document, such an event would be an alien taxon becoming a
1308 harmful invasive species. Risk assessment is part of risk analysis. Risk analysis is
1309 comprised of risk assessment, risk management and risk communication.

1310 **Risk management:** The process of assessing options by which the risks of an event (its
1311 likelihood and/or consequence) can be reduced or mitigated.

1312 **Introduction status:** Whether a taxon is found in an area to which it is not native (alien),
1313 and how far along the introduction-naturalisation-invasion continuum it has reached.
1314 Ideally as per the Blackburn et al. (2011) framework

1315 **Vector:** A mechanism responsible for the transport of species to new areas where they did
1316 not previously occur. A pathway (for example shipping) could have several vectors
1317 associated with it (for example in cargo, in passenger luggage, on passengers or crew
1318 themselves, in ballast water, or attached to the hull).

1319

1320 **Appendix S2 Guidance for confidence classification**

1321 Process is adapted from IUCN (2020b).

1322

Sources of uncertainty that influence the confidence rating	Presence of confounding effects	Study design	Data quality and type	Spatial and temporal scale	Coherence of evidence
High confidence: it is likely (approximately 90% chance) that the true Response is equal to the assigned one	The likelihood of the presence of confounding effects is low	The study design would have allowed the detection of higher/lower or different Response levels than the one assigned	There is relevant direct observational evidence to support the assessment; the data are reliable and of good quality	Evidence was recorded at the typical spatial and temporal scales	All evidence points in the same direction (no contradictory evidence)
Medium confidence: there is potential for the true Response to be different from the assigned one (approximately 65-75% chance of the assigned Response being correct)	Confounding effects may be at least partly responsible for the observed Response	The study design would not have allowed the detection of higher/lower or different Response levels than the one assigned (i.e. it cannot be reasonably excluded)	There is some direct observational evidence to support the assessment, but some of the data are inferred	Evidence was recorded at a spatial or temporal scale which may not be relevant, but extrapolation or downscaling of the data to relevant scales is considered reliable or embraces little uncertainty	Most evidence points in the same direction, but some is contradictory or ambiguous
Low confidence: it is likely that the true Response is different from the assigned one (approximately 35% chance of the assigned Response being correct)	The likelihood of confounding effects being present is high	The study design does not allow any conclusions about higher or lower Response levels and it is likely that the true Response level is higher or lower	There is no direct observational evidence to support the assessment; data are of low quality	Evidence was recorded at a spatial or temporal scale which is unlikely to be relevant, and extrapolation or downscaling of the data to relevant scales is considered unreliable or embraces significant uncertainties	Data are strongly ambiguous, or contradictory

1323

Appendix S3 Introduction pathways

Details are as per Harrower et al. (2018).

Release
Release:BiologicalControl
Release:StabilisationAndBarriers
Release:FisheryInWild
Release:Hunting
Release:AestheticRelease
Release:ConservationInWild
Release:OtherRelease
Escape
Escape:Agriculture
Escape:Aquaculture
Escape:BotanicalGardensAndZoos
Escape:Pet
Escape:FarmedAnimals
Escape:Forestry
Escape:FurFarms
Escape:Horticulture
Escape:Ornamental
Escape:Research
Escape:LiveFoodAndLiveBait
Escape:OtherEscape
Contaminant
Contaminant:NurseryMaterialContaminant
Contaminant:BaitContaminant
Contaminant:FoodContaminant
Contaminant:ContaminantOfAnimals
Contaminant:ParasiteOfAnimals
Contaminant:ContaminantOfPlants
Contaminant:ParasiteOfPlants
Contaminant:SeedContaminant
Contaminant:TimberTradeContaminant
Contaminant:HabitatMaterialContaminant
Contaminant:OtherContaminant
Stowaway
Stowaway:FishingEquipment
Stowaway:ContainerAndBulkCargo
Stowaway:Airplane
Stowaway:ShipExcludingBallastWaterOrHullFouling
Stowaway:MachineryAndEquipment
Stowaway:PeopleAndLuggage
Stowaway:PackingMaterial
Stowaway:BallastWater
Stowaway:HullFouling
Stowaway:LandVehicles
Stowaway:OtherStowaway
Corridors
Corridors:CanalsAndArtificialWaterways
Corridors:TunnelsAndBridges
Unaided:NaturalDispersal
Unknown

Appendix S4 Version history

v1.0: Kumschick, S., Wilson, J. R., Foxcroft, L.C. (2017) Guidelines for conducting risk analyses under the NEM:BA Alien and Invasive Species Regulations of 2014. Submitted to the South African Department of Environmental Affairs, March 2017.

v1.1: Kumschick, S., Wilson, J.R., Foxcroft, L.C. (2018) Framework and Guidelines for Conducting Risk Analyses for Alien Species. Preprints 2018, 2018110551, <http://dx.doi.org/10.20944/preprints201811.0551.v1>

v1.2: Kumschick, S., Wilson, J.R.U., Foxcroft, L.C. (2020) A framework to support alien species regulation: the Risk Analysis for Alien Taxa (RAAT). *NeoBiota* 62: 213–239. doi.org/10.3897/neobiota.62.51031.

v2.0 (and future versions): to be available from Zenodo.
<https://zenodo.org/record/4017196>

Appendix S5 Reporting template

Risk Analysis Report

Taxon:		Area:	
Listing under NEM:BA A&IS lists of 2020:			
Compiled by:		Approved by:	
Picture of Taxon		Alien distribution map	
Source:		Reference:	
Risk Assessment summary:			Risk score:
Risk Management summary:			
Recommendations:			
Recommended listing category:			
Recommended prohibitions or exemptions:			
Is a change to nomenclature recommended:			
Should the recommendation be revisited within 5 years:			

Suggested citation: XXX
 XXX
 XXX

1. Background

BAC1 Name of assessor(s)	
Name of lead assessor	
Additional assessor (1)	
Additional assessor (2)	
Assessor for correspondence	
BAC2 Contact details of assessor(s)	
Lead assessor	Organisational affiliation:
	email:
	Phone:
Additional assessor (1)	Organisational affiliation:
	email:
	Phone:
Additional assessor (2)	Organisational affiliation:
	email:
	Phone:
BAC3 Name(s) and contact details of expert(s) consulted	
Expert (1)	Name:
	email:
	Phone:
Expert (2)	Name:
	email:
	Phone:
Comments:	
BAC4 Scientific name of <i>Taxon</i> under assessment	
<i>Taxon</i> name:	Authority:
Comments:	
References:	
BAC5 Synonym(s) considered	
Synonyms:	
Comments:	
References:	
BAC6 Common name(s) considered	
Common names:	
Comments:	
References:	
BAC7 What is the native range of the <i>Taxon</i>?	
Response:	Confidence:
Comments:	
References:	
BAC8 What is the global alien range of the <i>Taxon</i>?	
Response:	Confidence:
Comments:	
References:	

BAC9 Geographic scope = the Area under consideration			
Area of assessment:			
Comments:			
BAC10 Is the <i>Taxon</i> present in the Area?			
Response:			Confidence:
Comments:			
References:			
BAC11 Evidence of presence			
Physical specimen		Source:	
Molecular confirmation		Source:	
Literature reference		Source:	
Field observation		Source:	
BAC12 Is the <i>Taxon</i> native to the Area or part of the Area?			
Response:			Confidence:
Comments:			
References:			
BAC13 What is the <i>Taxon</i>'s introduction status in the Area?			
The <i>Taxon</i> is in captivity or cultivation			Confidence:
The <i>Taxon</i> is present outside of captivity or cultivation			Confidence:
The <i>Taxon</i> is established			Confidence:
The <i>Taxon</i> is invasive			Confidence:
Comments:			
References:			
BAC14 How did (or does) the <i>Taxon</i> arrive in the Area?			
Pathway:			Confidence:
Pathway:			Confidence:
Comments:			
References:			
BAC15 Is the <i>Taxon</i> regulated in the Area?			
Response:			Confidence:
Comments:			
Version of the regulations		Regulatory name	
Common name(s)		Any previous names used	
Category			
Exemptions or Prohibitions			

2. Likelihood

LIK1 Likelihood of entry via unaided primary pathways	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	

LIK2 Likelihood of entry via human aided primary pathways	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	

LIK3 Habitat suitability	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	

LIK4 Climate suitability	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	

LIK5 Unaided secondary (dispersal) pathways	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	

LIK6 Human aided secondary (dispersal) pathways	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	

3. Consequences

CON1 Environmental impact	
CON1a: Competition	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON1b: Predation	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON1c: Hybridisation	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON1d: Transmission of disease	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON1e: Parasitism	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON1f: Poisoning/toxicity	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON1g: Bio-fouling or other direct physical disturbance	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON1h: Grazing/herbivory/browsing	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON1i: Chemical, physical or structural impact on ecosystem	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON1k: Indirect impacts through interactions with other species	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON1 Maximum environmental impact	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON2 Socio-economic impact	
CON2a: Safety	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	

References:	
CON2b: Material and immaterial assets	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON2c: Health	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON2d: Social, spiritual and cultural relations	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON2 Maximum socio-economic impact	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON3 Potential impact	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	

4. Risk Assessment calculations

Likelihood =

Parameter	Likelihood	Stages	Final assessment
LIK1		P(entry) =	P (invasion) =
LIK2			
LIK3		P(establishment) =	
LIK4			
LIK5		P (spread) =	
LIK6			

Consequence =

Parameter	Mechanism/sector	Response
CON1a	Competition	
CON1b	Predation	
CON1c	Hybridisation	
CON1d	Disease transmission	
CON1e	Parasitism	
CON1f	Poisoning/toxicity	
CON1g	Bio-fouling or other direct physical disturbance	
CON1h	Grazing/herbivory/browsing	
CON1i	Chemical, physical, structural impact	
CON1k	Indirect impacts through interactions with other species	
CON1	Maximum environmental impact	
CON2a	Safety	
CON2b	Material and immaterial assets	
CON2c	Health	
CON2d	Social, spiritual and cultural relations	
CON2	Maximum socio-economic impact	
CON3	Potential impact	

Risk score =

		Consequence				
		MC	MN	MO	MR	MV
Likelihood	Extremely unlikely	low	low	low	medium	medium
	Very unlikely	low	low	low	medium	high
	Unlikely	low	low	medium	high	high
	Fairly probable	medium	medium	high	high	high
	Probable	medium	high	high	high	high

5. Management

MAN1 What is the feasibility to stop future immigration?	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	

MAN2 Benefits of the Taxon					
MAN2a Socio-economic benefits of the <i>Taxon</i>					
Benefit	Magnitude	Current?	Replaceability	Stakeholders	Confidence
Rationale:					
References:					
MAN2b Environmental benefits of the <i>Taxon</i>					
Benefit	Magnitude	Current?	Replaceability	Stakeholders	Confidence
Rationale:					
References:					

MAN3 Can the risk be reduced?	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
MAN3a Do some entities of the <i>Taxon</i> pose a reduced risk?	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
MAN3b Is the risk of the <i>Taxon</i> reduced under certain environmental conditions?	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
MAN3c Can containment options reduce the risk of the <i>Taxon</i>?	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
MAN3d Is management in place that can reduce the invasion or impact of the <i>Taxon</i>?	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	

MAN4 Should eradication be considered as a management goal?	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	

6. Recommendations

REC1 What are the options for regulation of the <i>Taxon</i>?
Options for regulation:
Rationale:
Recommendation:
References:

Appendix BAC7 (native range of the *Taxon*):

Appendix BAC8 (global alien range of the *Taxon*):

Appendix BAC10 (range of the *Taxon* in the *Area*):